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Reaction of Guanidine with 3-Formyl Chromones

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GOSH *et al*¹ observed that reaction of 3-formyl chromone with guanidine carbonate (in 1 : 2 molar ratio) in ethanol or acetic acid yields 2-amino-5-hydroxy-5H-[1]benzopyrano[4,3-d]pyrimidine (A), while the reaction under similar conditions of 4-oxo-4H-[1]benzopyran-3-carboxylate (C) with guanidine carbonate yields 2-amino-[1]benzopyrano[4,3-d]pyrimidine-(4H)one (B).

Considering the susceptibility of γ -pyrone nucleus towards alkaline solution, these reactions are likely to follow a different path under basic conditions. 3-Formyl chromones prepared by Vilsmeier-Haack reaction²⁻⁵ on *o*-hydroxy acetophenones were therefore condensed with guanidine hydrochloride in alkaline medium and the products isolated and their structures determined.

There is a possibility of the formation of two different pyrimidines (Ia or II) when 3-formyl chromones are condensed with guanidine under basic conditions. In order to find out which one of these compounds is actually formed the following set of reactions was carried out.

The oximes of the isolated products were subjected to Beckmann rearrangement in presence of dimethylformamide and phosphorous oxychloride which yielded the corresponding benzoxazole derivatives (Ie-Xe). The oximeacetates swiftly cyclised in dry pyridine to the corresponding benzisoxazole derivatives (Id-Xd). It can therefore be safely concluded that when guanidine and 3-formyl chromones are condensed in basic medium there is a formation of 5-salicyloyl-2-amino-pyrimidines (Ia).

IR (KBr) of 5-salicyloyl-2-amino-pyrimidines (Ia-XIa) showed bands at 1640 (C=O), 3140 (phenolic OH), 3400 and 3300 cm^{-1} (asymmetric and symmetric stretch of $-\text{NH}_2$).

NMR (CDCl_3) of 5-(5'-ethyl-*o*-hydroxybenzoyl)-2-amino pyrimidine (XIIa) showed the following signals :

τ 1.2 (J = 7Hz 3H - CH_2CH_3), 2.6 (dd, J = 7Hz, 2H - CH_2CH_3), 5.7 (s, 2H - NH_2), 6.8-7.6 (m, 3H aromatic), 8.7 (d 2H, 4 and 6 - H of pyrimidine ring), 11.55 (s, 1H phenolic OH).

IR (KBr) of oximes (Ib-XIb) of 5-salicyloyl pyrimidines showed bands at 3150 (phenolic OH), 3600 (N-OH), 1660 (C=N), 3455 and 3290 cm^{-1} (asymmetric and symmetric stretch of $-\text{NH}_2$).

IR (KBr) of oxime acetates (Ic-Xc) showed bands at 3180 (phenolic OH), 3390 and 3180 (asymmetric and symmetric stretch of $-\text{NH}_2$), 1780 (N-OAc) and 1655 cm^{-1} (C=N).

IR (KBr) of benzisoxazoles (Id-Xd) showed bands at 3320 and 3140 (asymmetric and symmetric stretch of $-\text{NH}_2$), 808 cm^{-1} (benzisoxazole ring stretch).

TABLE I—SUBSTITUTED 5-SALICYLOYL-2-AMINOPYRIMIDINES (Ia-XIa) AND THE OXIMES (Ib-XIb)

No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	m.p. °C	Molecular formula
Ia	H	H	H	210 ^a	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂	Ib	H	H	H	200 ^a	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂
IIa	CH ₃	H	H	220 ^a	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂	IIb	CH ₃	H	H	205 ^a	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂
IIIa	H	CH ₃	H	200 ^a	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂	IIIb	H	CH ₃	H	187 ^a	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂
IVa	H	H	CH ₃	210 ^a	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂	IVb	H	H	CH ₃	220 ^a	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂
Va	Cl	H	H	287 ^b	C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	Vb	H	H	Cl	226 ^a	C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂ Cl
VIa	H	H	Cl	230 ^c	C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	VIb	H	H	Br	220 ^a	C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂ Br
VIIa	H	H	Br	240 ^a	C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂ Br	VIIb	H	H	C ₂ H ₅	210 ^a	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂
VIIIa	CH ₃	H	Cl	240 ^c	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	VIIIb	CH ₃	H	Cl	242 ^b	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl
IXa	H	CH ₃	Cl	276 ^b	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	IXb	H	CH ₃	Cl	265 ^b	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl
Xa	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	238 ^a	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂	Xb	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	241 ^d	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂
XIa	Cl	H	Cl	260 ^b	C ₁₁ H ₇ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	XIb	Br	H	Br	271 ^e	C ₁₁ H ₇ O ₂ N ₂ Br
XIIa	H	H	C ₂ H ₅	183 ^a	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂						

All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses.

Crystallized from (a) alcohol, (b) acetic acid, (c) alcohol + acetic acid, (d) methanol, (e) dioxane.

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TABLE 2—OXIME ACETATES OF 5-SALICYLOYL-2-AMINOPYRIMIDINES (Ic-Xc) : 5-[3-(1,2-BENZISOXAZOLYL)]-2-AMINOPYRIMIDINES (Id-Xd)

No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	m.p. °C	Molecular formula
Ic	H	H	H	244 ^b	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₄	Id	H	H	H	285°	C ₁₇ H ₉ ON ₄
IIc	CH ₃	H	H	205 ^a	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₄	IIId	OH ₃	H	H	290 ^a	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ ON ₄
IIIc	H	OH ₃	H	200°	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₄	IIIId	H	OH ₃	H	272°	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ ON ₄
IVc	H	H	CH ₃	210°	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₄	IVd	H	H	CH ₃	255 ^b	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ ON ₄
Vc	H	H	Cl	200°	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₄ Cl	Vd	H	H	Cl	307 ^b	C ₁₁ H ₇ ON ₄ Cl
VIc	H	H	Br	208°	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₄ Br	VIId	H	H	Br	312°	C ₁₁ H ₇ ON ₄ Br
VIIc	H	H	C ₆ H ₅	212°	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₄	VIIId	H	H	C ₆ H ₅	180 ^a	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ ON ₄
VIIIc	OH ₃	H	Cl	220 ^a	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₄ Cl	VIIIId	OH ₃	H	CH ₃	260 ^a	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ ON ₄
IXc	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	208 ^a	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₄	IXd	OH ₃	H	Cl	230°	C ₁₂ H ₉ ON ₄ Cl
Xc	Br	H	Br	250°	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₄ Br ₂	Xd	Br	H	Br	262°	C ₁₁ H ₇ ON ₄ Br ₂

All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses.
Solvents for crystallization same as in Table 1.

IR (KBr) of benzoxazoles (Ie-Xe) showed bands at 3340 and 3160 cm⁻¹ (asymmetric and symmetric stretch of -NH₂).

Experimental

5-Substituted salicyloyl-2-amino pyrimidines (Ia-XIa) (Scheme 1) :

A mixture of 3-formyl chromone (0.01 mol), guanidine hydrochloride (0.01 mol), potassium hydroxide (0.02 mol dissolved in 2-3 ml water) and alcohol (30 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The solid product obtained on acidification was washed with water and crystallised from proper solvent.

Scheme 1

Oximes (Ib-XIb) and their N-acetates (Ic-Xc) (Scheme 2) :

Oximes of 5-salicyloyl-2-amino pyrimidines were prepared⁶ by dissolving Ia-Xa (0.1 mol) in aqueous potassium hydroxide solution (40%) and adding to this the aqueous solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.4 mol) dropwise with constant stirring at 10-15° for 2 h. The oximes precipitated on acidification were washed with water, filtered and crystallised from proper solvent.

N-Acetates of the oximes were prepared by heating the oxime (0.1 mol) with acetic anhydride (0.12 mole) in a water bath till the oxime dissolved completely. The solution was kept at room temperature for 2 h and poured over crushed ice. The solid obtained was washed with water, filtered and crystallised from proper solvent.

Cyclisation of N-acetates (Ic-Xc) to 1,2-benzisoxazoles (Id-Xd) :

N-Acetate (1 g) was refluxed in dry pyridine⁷ (10-15 ml) for 4 h. The reaction mixture was then poured on ice and dil. HCl. The solid thus obtained was washed with sodium hydroxide (2%) to remove uncyclised N-acetate, filtered and crystallised from proper solvent.

Scheme 2

Beckmann rearrangement of the oximes (Ib-Xb) (Scheme 3) :

Ib-XIb (1 g) was dissolved in dimethylformamide (8-10 ml) and the solution was ice cooled. To this phosphorous oxychloride⁸⁻¹⁰ was added dropwise with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 2 h and then poured

TABLE 3—5-[2-(BENZOXAZOLYL)]-2-AMINO PYRIMIDINES (Ie-Xe)

No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	m.p. °C	Molecular formula
Ie	H	H	H	305 ^f	C ₁₁ H ₈ ON ₄
IIe	CH ₃	H	H	260 ^b	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ ON ₄
IIIe	H	CH ₃	H	282 ^f	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ ON ₄
IVe	H	H	CH ₃	292°	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ ON ₄
Ve	H	H	Cl	270°	C ₁₁ H ₇ ON ₄ Cl
VIe	H	H	Br	275 ^b	C ₁₁ H ₇ ON ₄ Br
VIIe	H	H	C ₆ H ₅	220°	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ ON ₄
VIIIe	CH ₃	H	Cl	302 ^b	C ₁₂ H ₉ ON ₄ Cl
IXe	H	CH ₃	Cl	316 ^f	C ₁₂ H ₉ ON ₄ Cl
Xe	Cl	H	Cl	270 ^b	C ₁₁ H ₇ ON ₄ Cl ₂

All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses.
Crystallized from (a) alcohol, (b) acetic acid, (f) pyridine.

over crushed ice. The solid obtained was washed with sodium hydroxide (2%) to remove uncyclised oxime, filtered and crystallised from proper solvent.

Scheme 3

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[1,3,4]Thiadiazolo[2,3-c][1,2,4]triazines

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ALTHOUGH a number of [1,3,4]thiadiazolo[2,3-c][1,2,4]triazines are known¹⁻⁴, no attempt seems to have been made so far for the synthesis of their 2,3-dihydro derivatives. We report here the syntheses of some 5-oxo-2,3-dihydro-5H-[1,3,4]thiadiazolo[2,3-c][1,2,4]triazines with substitutions in positions 2 and 6. These have been prepared by the condensation of 4-amino-5-oxo-3-thioxo-6-substituted-2,3,4,5-tetrahydro[1,2,4]triazines (I) with various aldehydes. Structure III for these compounds finds support from analytical results, ir and pmr data. IR of IIIa

gave a band at 1670 due to amide while the NH band appeared at 3170 cm⁻¹. PMR of IIIa in DMSO-d₆ (chemical shifts in δ ppm) showed a sharp singlet (3H) at 2.3, assignable to three protons

of methyl group at C-6 (CH₃-C(=O)-). The five aromatic protons and one benzylic proton at C-2 merged to give a multiplet (6H) at 7.50-8.50. The structure IIIa finds further support from its insolubility in dil. sodium hydroxide solution.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries in paraffin bath and are uncorrected. IR spectrum was recorded in nujol on Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer and pmr on Varian EM 390 90 MHz spectrometer using TMS as the internal reference. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel plates.

4-Amino-5-oxo-3-thioxo-6-substituted-2,3,4,5-tetrahydro[1,2,4]triazines (I): These were prepared starting from thiocarbohydrazide⁵ and pyruvic acid or benzoylformic acid according to the procedure of Dornow *et al.*⁶

6-Methyl-2-phenyl-5-oxo-2,3-dihydro-5H-[1,3,4]thiadiazolo[2,3-c][1,2,4]triazines (IIIa): Dry hydrochloric acid gas was passed through a chilled ethereal suspension (20 ml) of 4-amino-6-methyl-5-oxo-3-thioxo-2,3,4,5-tetrahydro[1,2,4]triazine (Ia, R = CH₃; 1.58 g, 0.01 mol) till it was saturated. After decanting off the ethereal layer, the solid mass was suspended in absolute ethanol (40 ml). To this was added benzaldehyde (1.06 g, 0.01 mol) and fused sodium acetate (0.82 g, 0.01 mol) and the contents refluxed on steam bath under nitrogen atmosphere (by continuous bubbling of dry nitrogen). As the reaction progressed the suspension dissolved with simultaneous separation of a new solid. Progress of the reaction was monitored by tlc at regular intervals. It was refluxed for 4 h in all. After concentration, it was cooled and the solid product was collected under suction, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol. Other aldehydes were also condensed with Ia under similar conditions.

4-Amino-5-oxo-6-phenyl-3-thioxo-2,3,4,5-tetrahydro[1,2,4]triazine (Ib) was also condensed with

